

Crude Oil Exposure Affects Hepatic Function of Diabetic Wistar Rats Treated with Metformin and *Allium sativum*

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Abstract

Residential and occupational crude oil exposure has been linked to hematotoxicity but its effects on hepatotoxicity, especially in diabetic state is an emerging area. This research investigated the effect of 5% crude oil exposure on hepatic function of diabetic Wistar rats treated with metformin with a view to determine if and how exposure to crude oil impacted diabetes management. The diabetes was induced by intra-peritoneal injection of 65mg/kg streptozocin (STZ) dissolved in citrate buffer which was confirmed 48 h after the injection. Rats were grouped into six (6) groups of five (5) rats each; group 1 was the normal control, group two was diabetic positive control group, group three was diabetic group treated with 250 mg/kg b.w. metformin, group four was diabetic untreated group exposed to 5% crude oil, group five was diabetic group treated with 250mg/kg b.w. metformin exposed to 5% crude oil, group six was diabetic rats treated with 200mg/kg b.w. of *Allium sativum* (garlic) extract plus 250 mg/kg b.w. metformin, exposed to 5% crude oil. The Rats were subjected to treatment for four weeks. Diabetic control animals had high activity of ALT, rise in AST activity was found in diabetic rats treated with standard, diabetic positive control and diabetic animals exposed to crude oil. Rats that received both the extract of *Allium sativum* plus standard drug (metformin) had normal level of aspartate aminotransferase (AST) as was in normal control animals. There was no significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in activity of alkaline phosphatase (ALP) in all groups compared with normal control except standard drug treated group. Diabetic control rats and diabetic rats exposed to crude oil without treatment had high plasma protein content compared with other groups. The histological examination showed that normal control animals and animals treated with the aqueous extract of *Allium sativum* plus standard drug had normal features of hepatocytes; moderate hepatic necrosis in rats treated with standard drug but exposed to 5% crude oil; and normal hepatic features in diabetic animals treated with standard drug as well as diabetic positive control animals. Therefore, crude oil exposures affect liver function of diabetic animals under treatment with metformin by inducing inflammation and necrosis of hepatic tissue. Intake of *Allium sativum* would help protect and improve hepatic function of diabetic people living in environment with crude oil spillage/exposure.

Keywords: *Allium sativum*, Crude Oil, Diabetes Mellitus, Liver, Metformin

1.0 Introduction

Crude oil is naturally occurring unprocessed oil found in the earth crust derived from decaying plant and animals, deposited over a long period of time in lakes, seas, and swamp [1]. It contains varied levels of physical and chemical substances with potential toxicities [2]. Collectively, it contains diverse array of substances that produce definite physiological, biochemical and anatomic

changes. The most important of these include paraffin, naphthalene, volatile organic compounds (VOCs), heavy metals, sulfur, and oxygen among others. Each crude oil has its own peculiar properties that determine its toxicity [3]. These substances are essential but their impacts on health and people life quality are of immense concern.

In recent years, there has been a revival of interest on crude oil and petroleum hydrocarbons exploration/exposure which may exert pathological effects manifesting predominantly in a wide array of NCDs. Of these, cancer, diabetes mellitus, infertility, allergy, liver and kidney diseases were of major concerns. Many studies have demonstrated effect of crude oil and petroleum hydrocarbon exposure on diabetes mellitus [4], [5] reporting climbing number of morbidity and mortality burden. Diabetes mellitus is a serious health problem associated with impairment of liver function resulting in its dysfunction, and crude oil exposure potentiates the effects [4]. In Nigeria, the increasing population growth and expanding industrialization have led to increasing demand for petroleum energy leading to generation and discharge of petroleum wastes into the environment, which exposes living organisms including human to the hazardous effects of hydrocarbons [6]. The resultant effects on body systems are large and could be synergistic, additive or antagonistic that compromises body homeostasis with effects on several body organs [2].

Liver is one of the organs postulated to have impaired functions as a result of petroleum and related hydrocarbon exposures [6]. It is a central organ in the metabolic processes that converts xenobiotics into harmless hydrophilic metabolites for excretion [6]. However, evidence of the involvement of petroleum hydrocarbons exposure on secretion, synthetic and excretory functions of liver especially during treatment of diabetes is scarce. Assessment of hepatic functions would help identify the possible effects of petroleum exposures such that effective policies can be implemented to reduce the significant depletion in resources as a result of diagnosis and treatment, especially in the front-line areas where socioeconomic status of the inhabitants is generally poor [1]. The present study investigated the effect of crude oil exposure on liver function indices of diabetic rats treated with metformin with a view to highlight the effect or otherwise on diabetes management. This would enable the concerned individuals and stakeholders to make decisions and provide comprehensive strategies on healthy living of residents to avoid compounding issues. Metformin was the drug of choice in this study due to its antioxidant, insulin sensitizing effects in addition to its effect of reduced hepatic glucose production, which reduces inflammation and oxidative stress burden

posed on the pancreas upon streptozocin injection to rats thereby improving glucose metabolism.

Nowadays, primary health care is ensured with the use of herbs and spices by about 80% of the world population being them cheap, affordable, acceptable and less toxic than current modern day drugs [7]. They contain wide range of chemicals that serve as antioxidants, detoxifiers, chelates transition metal ions, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobials and antiviral among numerous others. *Allium sativum* is herb and spice demonstrated to possess above potentials [7]. *Allium sativum* L. It belongs to the family Liliaceae, commonly called Garlic in English and *Tafarnuwa* in Hausa (Nigeria). It is a fragrant herb and tuber-derived spice widely used as a flavoring ingredient and therapeutic purposes of many diseases in the world. Its anti-carcinogenic, antihypertensive, immune-modulatory, antioxidant, antiviral, anti-microbial, anti-diabetic, and hypolipidaemic effects were reported [7]. *Allium sativum* being a detoxification, hypoglycemic and anti-diabetic agent, its use in the present study could provide protection against the damaging effect of crude oil exposure and that of diabetes mellitus. Thus, the present study.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

2.1.1 Crude oil and standard drug

Bonny Light Crude oil for the study was obtained from Ebedei Oil Terminal, Delta State, Nigeria. Standard drug (metformin) was purchased from Albarka Yazid Medicine Store, Dutsin-Ma. It was a product of Ashkar Pharm India.

2.1.2 Plant material and preparation

Allium sativum was purchased from Chake Market, Katsina, Katsina State, Nigeria. It was identified and authenticated at Herbarium of the Department of Biology, Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. It sliced into small pieces, air dried under the shade and grinded into powder using pestle and mortar and stored in sealed plastic container until required.

2.1.3 Experimental animals and management

A total of thirty (30) albino rats weighing between 150-200g were purchased from animal house, Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Ahmadu Bello

University, Zaria, Nigeria. They were fed normal animal feed (Broiler starter, Ultima Chikun, Kaduna Nigeria) and allowed access to clean water *ad libitum*. The rats were kept in wire mesh cages for a period of two weeks to acclimatize before the commencement of the experiment.

2.2.0 Methods

2.2.1 Plant Material Extraction

Allium sativum was sliced in to small pieces, air dried at room temperature for five days, pulverized into powder using pestle and mortar, and then stored in sealed plastic containers until required. Exactly 200g of the powdered plant was soaked into 600 ml of distilled water for 48 h, and then filtered with Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The extract was concentrated using water bath maintained at a temperature of 40°C, and stored at 40c until required.

2.2.2 Induction of Diabetes

Diabetes was induced by a single intra-peritoneal injection of 65 mg/kg streptozocin (sigma St Louis, M.O., USA) dissolved in 0.9% citrate buffer to overnight fasted rats using insulin syringe. Diabetes mellitus was confirmed after 72 hours of streptozocin administration by measuring fasting blood glucose of overnight of fasted animals (FBG). The ACCU CHECK Glucometer was used to measure the glucose with compatible strip. Rats with FBG >8.0 mmol/l were considered diabetic [6].

2.2.3 Animal grouping and experimental protocol

Rats in this study were grouped as:

Group 1: Normal control rats, received food and water only.

Group 2: Streptozocin induced diabetic rats, received no treatment.

Group 3: Streptozocin induced diabetic rats, exposed to 5% crude oil, receive no treatment.

Group 4: Streptozocin induced diabetic rats, treated with metformin (250mg/kg b.w.) for four weeks.

Group 5: Streptozocin induced diabetic rats, exposed to 5% crude oil, treated with 250 mg/kg b.w of metformin for four weeks.

Group 6: Streptozocin induced diabetic rats, exposed to 5% crude oil, treated with 200 mg/kg b.w. of *A. sativum* extract and 250 mg/kg b.w. of metformin for four weeks.

Body weight

The body weight of all the animals before induction and within days of treatment were weekly recorded using digital weighing balance M-METLAR (QC PASS KH03).

2.10 Blood sample collection and clinical chemistry

Twenty-four hour after the last treatment, rats were fasted 12 hours after which they were anaesthetized by dropping individual animal in a plastic jar saturated with diethyl ether vapour. The rats were then removed from the jar and blood samples collected through cardiac puncture into labeled plastic specimen bottles containing heparin. They were then centrifuged at 4000 g for ten minutes to obtain plasma which was pipetted into specimen test tubes for other biochemical analyses.

2.11 Determination of biochemical parameters

Total protein was estimated using the biuret reaction method by [8]. Serum albumin was determined using Bromocresol green (BCG) binding method as described and modified by Doumas et al. [9]. Alkaline phosphatase activity was estimated using the method of [10]. Alanine transaminase and Asparate amino tranferase were measured according to the method described by Reitman and Frankel [11].

2.12 Statistical analysis

The data obtained were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, and analyzed using Statistical [Package for Social Science SPSS version 22 software. The significance among groups was determined by One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Means regarded significant at $P < 0.05$.

3.0 Results

Administration of extract and standard to the rats caused reduced reaction to noise, slow movement and resting at the corner of cages. It was also observed that rats that were injected with streptozocin had a watery stool, brownish urine and hair loss which was found to reduced/ turn to normal three days of extract administration. Also, diabetic rats that received standard drug and those exposed to crude oil plus standard drug were found to look so sick, with their heads down on the floor indicating some aspects of worry and feeling disturbed. This was not seen in rats that received the extract plus standard drug despite crude oil exposure.

The results of the effect of treatment with aqueous extract of *A. sativum* and standard drug on body weight changes of diabetic rats are presented in Table 1. The results indicate that streptozotocin injection resulted in drastic decrease in body weight of rats compared with that of normal control. Administration of the extract and standard drug (metformin) resulted significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in body weight of the rats compared with untreated diabetic rats and untreated diabetic rats exposed to crude oil. There was no statistically significant change in body weight of the rats treated with the extract (200mg/kg) plus standard drug (250mg/kg) compared to normal control in the first week of treatment. The same effect was observed for diabetic rats treated with standard. However, after 14 days of treatment, the body weight increase significantly ($p < 0.05$) in rats that received the extract and standard drug despite exposure to crude oil.

The results of the effect of treatment with extract and standard drug on liver function indices are presented in Table 2. The result indicates that untreated diabetic rats had higher Alanine transaminase (ALT) activity. Anon-significant increase ($p > 0.05$) in the activity of aspartate aminotransferase (AST) of diabetic rats treated with standard drug, untreated diabetic rats and diabetic rats exposed to crude oil was found. The result indicates rats that received both the extract and standard drug had normal levels of AST as was in normal control rats. Diabetic rats treated with standard drug had a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in the activity of alkaline phosphatase (ALP) compared with normal control rats (Table 2). Untreated diabetic rats and diabetic rats exposed to crude oil without treatment had high plasma protein content compared with other groups including normal control rats (Table 2). This was supported by results from histological examination of hepatic cells of control and experimental (diabetic) rats treated with aqueous extract of *Allium sativum* and standard drug (metformin); exposed to crude oil for four weeks (Plates 1.a-f). From the plates, both the normal control rats and rats treated with the aqueous extract plus standard drug had normal features of the liver cells (hepatocytes); there was moderate hepatic necrosis in rats treated with standard drug but exposed to 5% crude oil; and normal hepatic features in diabetic rats treated with standard drug as well as untreated diabetic rats

Table 1: Effect of garlic extract and standard drug on body weight of rats injected with streptozocin

Groups	Initial	Weekly Weight (g)			
		1	2	3	4
A	132.4±20.42	148.2±11.69 ^b	169.6±16.13 ^a	196.0±13.29 ^a	205.6±14.30 ^a
B	120.8±33.2	147.7±40.63 ^b	125.1±57.9 ^c	108.1±61.08 ^d	105.4±81.07 ^c
C	134.2±20.86	174.1±31.18 ^a	147.6±27.21 ^b	136.8±30.13 ^c	126.8±32.98 ^b
D	124.0±29.31	146.4±25.71 ^b	124.8±20.58 ^c	130.9±16.0 ^c	126.8±16.20 ^b
E	103.5±14.06	146.3±17.33 ^b	121.5±20.96 ^c	160.1±27.56 ^b	154.6±18.44 ^b
F	99.8±16.36	127.4±24.46 ^c	104.5±39.6 ^d	146.0±15.96 ^b	144.8±13.53 ^b

Values are Mean ± Standard Deviation for five animals per group. A: Normal Control; B: Diabetic Control; C: Diabetes + Standard Drug; D: Diabetes +5% Crude Oil, No Treatment; E: Diabetes + 5% Crude Oil + Standard Drug; F: Diabetes + 5% Crude Oil + Garlic + Standard Drug.

Table 2: Liver function indices of experimental rats exposed to crude oil

Group	Parameters				
	ALT	AST	ALP	TP	ALB
A	2.25±0.24 ^b	30.50±4.36 ^b	18.33±3.10 ^a	1.10±0.24 ^c	0.7±0.14 ^c
B	22.50±2.46 ^b	20.00±3.83 ^b	21.60±4.14 ^a	2.13±0.18 ^{bc}	0.63±0.24 ^c
C	5.00±0.46 ^b	55.50±4.04 ^a	12.95±3.52 ^b	3.55±0.98 ^{ab}	1.05±0.29 ^{bc}
D	81.00±8.34 ^a	60.00±10.49 ^a	18.55±2.94 ^a	4.70±0.81 ^a	1.20±0.58 ^b
E	28.00±1.15 ^b	69.00±3.46 ^a	19.90±4.96 ^a	4.35±0.64 ^a	2.85±0.17 ^a
F	7.40±1.82 ^b	20.60±6.43 ^b	17.60±2.04 ^b	2.66±0.42 ^{ab}	1.00±0.22 ^{bc}

Values are mean ±standard deviation for 5 animals. Different superscript in the same column are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. ALT: Alanine aminotransferase, AST: Aspartate aminotransferase, ALP: Alkaline Phosphatase, TP: Total Protein, ALB: Albumin.

A: Diabetic animals given standard drug, exposed to 5% Crude Oil.

B: Diabetic animals given Garlic extract and standard drug, exposed to Crude Oil.

C: Diabetic animals treated with standard drug only; D: Diabetic Control Animals

E: Diabetes + Crude Oil, No Treatment; F: Normal Control Animals

Plate 1a: Normal features of

Plate 1b: Normal feature with slight changes in hepatocyteliver cells

Plate 1c: Necrosis of the hepatocytes

1d: Slight necrosis of hepatocyte and inflammation

1e: Necrosis with deep inflammation

1f: necrosis of hepatocytes and slight congestion

Plate 1: Histological examination of liver of control and rats treated with 200mg/kg body weight aqueous extract of *A. sativum* extract and 250mg/kg body weight standard drug exposed to 5% crude oil for four weeks. Normal control group (4.3a); diabetic animals treated with garlic extract plus standard, exposed to 5% crude oil (4.3b); diabetic animals treated with standard drug exposed to 5% crude oil (4.3c); diabetic animals treated with standard drug (4.3d); diabetic control group (4.3e); diabetic animals exposed to 5% crude oil without treatment (4.3f). The red arrow indicates necrosis, yellow arrow indicates inflammation or congestion.

4.0 Discussion

Streptozocin is considered one of the agents that induces diabetes mellitus as it causes serious disturbances in glucose metabolism by degeneration of pancreatic beta cells and accumulation of toxic free radicals leading to glycemic dysregulation [12][13]. In the present study, an attempt to identify whether or not exposure to crude oil affects hepatic functions of diabetic rats receiving treatment with Metformin was investigated.

It is well known that islets cells contains SOD, CAT and GSH activities in considerably moderate amounts which helps to maintain the shape, structure and function of the cells [12]. With injection of streptozocin however, there is considerably high generation of free radicals that induced cytotoxicity on the antioxidants enzymes. This in turn leads to reduction in the levels of insulin, culminating in alteration in glucose metabolism and utilization thereby causing hyperglycemia [12]. Hyperglycemia generally causes elevated serum glucose and oxidative stress indices. In this study, it was observed that injection of streptozocin to the rats caused appearance of most symptoms of diabetes mellitus, including the hyperglycemia, polydipsia, polyuria, decrease in body mass and increase in food and water intake [13].

In the present study, the decrease in weight of streptozocin-induced diabetic rats compared to the normal control rats could be due to selective destruction of pancreatic beta cells of islets of Langerhans by streptozocin which caused hypoinsulinemia with a consequent decrease in peripheral uptake and utilization of glucose and increase in gluconeogenesis [13]. This caused increased degradation of structural proteins thereby affecting the body weight of the rats. During this study, the observed increase in the weight of diabetic rats treated with both the aqueous extract of *Allium sativum* and standard drug after the first week of administration may be a function of anti-diabetic effect of the drug and extract indicating synergistic effect. *Allium sativum* possess ability to reduce hyperglycemia and improve glucose metabolism which may lead to improve glucose uptake and utilization, decreased gluconeogenesis and increased glycogenesis which spares structural proteins from degradation thereby maintaining body weight [14].

Alteration in metabolic (synthetic and excretory) functions of the liver has been shown to occur in

organisms exposed to crude oil [15]. The results of the present study found a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in the activity of alanine aminotransferase enzyme (ALT) in the diabetic control rats. A significant increase in aspartate aminotransferase activity (AST) of diabetic rats treated with standard drug, exposed to 5% crude oil and diabetic rats exposed to crude oil without treatment was found. There was also a decrease in total protein of rats treated with standard drug, exposed to crude oil compared to diabetic control and diabetic rats exposed to crude oil. The increase in the ALT and AST activities suggest inflammation and necrosis of liver cells [16]. It also suggests leakage of enzymes into cellular fluid indicating hepatic impairment. The decreased in ALT observed in crude oil exposed rats treated with standard drug suggest impairment in liver function. The activity of AST was found to be the same in rats treated with combination of standard drug and extract as was in control rats but it was high in diabetic rats exposed to crude oil without treatment and diabetic control rats. Generally, serum or plasma aspartate aminotransferase and alanine aminotransferase are useful indices for identifying necrosis and inflammation of liver [16]. ALP activity was high in all diabetic groups compared to normal control and standard control group. The increase in the activity suggests liver damage, including obstructive liver disease [16]. Increased ALP activity suggests cholestatic disease [16]. Generally, ALT has highest concentration in the liver with skeletal muscle and kidney having lesser enzyme activity. Its measurement is more specific to liver than AST, and ALT activity is usually higher than AST activity in acute liver disease [16]. Besides liver, the placenta, bone and intestine are important sources of the ALP enzyme activity. As such, its activity increases in many clinical states; especially the liver and bones diseases. Therefore, plasma ALP is considered a diagnostic marker for screening and follow-up of cholestatic liver disease. Cholestatic liver diseases are the main and only liver disease responsible for increased in ALP activity [16].

The histological examination of control and experimental rats showed normal features of hepatocytes of control rats and rats that received 200mg/kg body weight of the *A. sativum* extract plus 250mg/kg body weight of standard drug metformin. This indicates ability of the extract to improve and or maintain normal cyto-architecture of the hepatocytes despite crude oil exposure [6]. This suggests the hepato-protective effect of the

extract. It was found that rats treated with standard drug, exposed to crude oil had changes in the hepatocytes, whereas rats in diabetic control group and diabetic rats exposed to crude oil with no treatment had tissue necrosis.

The hepato-protective effect of the extract is in line with reports from studies by [17], [18] and [19], all of whom found hepato-protective effect of aqueous extract of *Allium sativum* with no significant alteration of liver indices parameters. The hepato-protective effect of the extract may be due to the sulfur containing compounds in the garlic that are known to increase the GSH content of the liver cells in addition to other vitamins, minerals and flavonoids contents that were reported to have hepato-protective effect [20][21][22][23] and [24]. It was found that rats treated with standard drug, exposed to crude oil had changes in the hepatocytes, whereas rats in diabetic control group and diabetic rats exposed to crude oil with no treatment had tissue necrosis.

The increase in plasma total protein observed in diabetic control and diabetic rats exposed to crude oil without treatment may be due to dehydration or increased plasma immunoglobulin concentration due either to inflammation or infections [6]. This means that exposure to crude oil in the presence of diabetes has predisposed rats to infections and inflammations. This causes decreased resistance to stress. Crude oil has been shown to exert immune suppressive effect or immunotoxic effect due to various organic and inorganic chemicals present [2].

5.0 Conclusion

Crude oil exposure at 5% affects hepatic functions of diabetic rats by inducing necrosis and inflammation of hepatocytes despite treatment with metformin. This suggest that exposure to crude oil could interfere with diabetes management by interfering with normal hepatic functions. Dietary intake of *A. sativum* would help improve and or maintain normal hepatic functions of diabetic people living in environments with crude oil exploration and refining activities.

6.0 Recommendation

We recommend further studies to identify the molecular mechanism of the individual components of crude oil in the development of hepatic dysfunction.

7.0 Acknowledgement

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8.0 Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests

9.0 References

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